

BioDivER – an Earth Observation based environmental reporting tool

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Background

The EU Green Deal and other regulatory frameworks bring many mandatory and voluntary **ESG reporting obligations** to commercial entities. These include, among others, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), Lieferketten-Sorgfaltspflichten-Gesetz (LkSG), and the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD). At the same time, standards like **ESRS** (European Sustainability Reporting Standards) are being developed that provide a comprehensive set of data points and **economic and ecological variables** that companies have to disclose. However, companies often lack data access or methodology to report these metrics. How can **Earth Observation** data and derived products be used to inform these meet the reporting obligations? This is the central research question of **BioDivER** (BioDiversity Environmental Reporting).

Introduction

The idea

BioDivER aims at the development of an information platform in accordance with ESG reporting standards. Companies may provide a list of their sites and economic sector(s). **Time series** of EO-derived environmental datasets are then automatically analysed in the vicinity of the company sites and summarised in a report document. As a theoretical basis, we rely on the SEEA-EA based **ENCORE** framework to identify general dependencies, impacts and potential mitigation practices between economic sectors, ecosystems, and in consequence biodiversity. While biodiversity is hardly measurable by Earth Observation methods, it relies on stable ecosystems which in turn provide services that are important for economic activity. Thus, we use environmental data to map the provision of sector-relevant **ecosystem services** as well as **biodiversity-relevant metrics** in the vicinity of company sites.

Identification of relevant metrics

A main challenge is finding a sufficient overlap between **reporting standards, metrics, and environmental data availability**, for example:

ESRS E4-5 38a "Disclosure of conversion over time of land cover"

- This information can be directly extracted from time-series of EO-derived land-cover maps
- Land cover changes can be quantified depending on the spatial resolution and accuracy of the land cover product

ESRS SBM-3 16 a iii) "Breakdown of material sites located in or near biodiversity-sensitive areas"

- "biodiversity-sensitive-areas": data availability is incomplete or restricted (e.g. Key Biodiversity Areas KBA)
- Metric Frameworks such as Nature Positive Metrics¹ (NPM) or Essential Biodiversity Variables² (EBV)/Essential Ecosystem Service Variables (EESV) provide tangible proxies, e.g.
- *Proportion of Natural/semi-natural habitat in area [%]* (Nature Positive Metrics)

Input

EO-based Datasets

On top of representing relevant proxies to reporting metrics, datasets to be used in BioDivER must be available at global coverage and in multiple time steps in order to provide information at all company sites and to allow insights into trends. The datasets are continuously integrated in the BioDivER prototypical back-end. An ongoing exercise is the creation of a translation matrix between parameters assessed by BioDivER, ecosystem services, and ESRS reporting standards.

Parameter (time series)	Dataset Source	Link to frameworks (example)
Land Cover	Sentinel-2 ESRI ⁴	ESRS E4-5 38a etc.
Groundwater anomaly	GFZ Global Gravity-based Groundwater Product (G3P) ⁵	Ecosystem Services: Groundwater provision
Above-Ground-Biomass	ESA CCI ⁶	Ecosystem Services: Climate Regulation, Biomass provision
Natural/Non-Natural Areas	Land Cover & auxiliary datasets, own calculation	NPM: Proportion of natural/semi-natural habitat in area [%]
Forest/Non-Forest	Sentinel-1, own calculation	ESRS E4-5 38a etc.
Water Risk Indicators	WRI: Aqueduct 4.0 ⁷	Ecosystem services: Surface/Groundwater provision

Report generation

The key functionality of BioDivER is the automatic generation of a **report document** based on the geolocation of sites and economic sector of a company. This report contains a general description of sector dependent ecosystem impact and dependency ratings, a **trend analysis** of ecosystem service provision and relevant environmental metrics across all sites, and a detailed **site-specific breakdown** that allows to identify potentially problematic sites.

Implementation

Technical backend

The technical back-end of BioDivER is based on **actinia** - an open source REST API for scalable, distributed, high-performance processing of geographical data that uses mainly GRASS GIS for computational tasks. Its strength lies in its broad functionality for time series analyses, scalability and **straightforward expandability**. Custom GRASS GIS addons are developed that analyse time-series of geodata, extract relevant interdependencies based on economic sectors, and generate the report document in a standardised **automatic processing chain**. Data are kept and automatically updated in a GRASS GIS database.

User uptake

While numerous variables are defined by frameworks like ESRS or State of Nature (SON), it is yet unclear for which metrics and domains companies have the **largest information gaps** that BioDivER could support. Test users from different economic sectors and company sizes are involved in the development process from the beginning. Their feedback is crucial for the selection of the included metrics and required report format. First results show large differences in the current status of ESG-reporting. Different preferences also exist in terms of data-driven (statistical) vs. marketing-driven (success stories) reporting.

Time series of environmental data are analysed in the vicinity of company sites. This example (top) shows forest loss in Southwest Germany. Resulting statistics (e.g. land-cover change, groundwater availability) are analysed across time, key figures and visualisations are reported (right).

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